

The behavioral evidence of processing congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-perspective-related representations during both perspective judgments

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Abstract

Daily, we make visuospatial self-perspective judgments from our perspective (SPJ). However, social contexts often require imagining another viewpoint—visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT). VPT is costlier than SPJ, and gets even costlier in autism, schizophrenia, and aging. One explanation is interference from self-related representations. This interference may reflect a mechanism that processes various self- and other-related representations, supported by the temporoparietal junction (TPJ). Moreover, reportedly other-related representations also influence SPJ, though this remains debated. Another explanation for VPT difficulty is the mental body transformation needed to adopt another perspective at greater angular disparities between perspectives. However, studies often confounded angle with left/right representational incongruence between perspectives. In our previous iEEG study, we found robust TPJ activity during both SPJ and VPT, possibly reflecting the processing of self-other representations. To test whether self-other representations are processed during both perspective judgments, we analyzed behavioral data from the same participants. We

categorized trials by an object's left/right congruence between the perspectives. We hypothesized that if self-other representations are processed during both judgments, participants will show greater difficulty in incongruent vs. congruent scenarios during SPJ and VPT. Linear mixed model analysis confirmed this: for both SPJ and VPT, errors were higher on incongruent than congruent trials. These findings show that self-other representations are processed in both SPJ and VPT, and incongruent ones cause interference, highlight left/right congruence as a key factor in VPT studies, and motivate further research with a similar approach on TPJ's role in processing multimodal self-other representations.

1. Introduction

1.1 Cognitive processes involved in Self- and Other-perspective judgments

Judgments about visuospatial scenes can be made either from one's own perspective or any other perspective. Our default multisensory experience of a visuospatial scene, the experience gathered from multiple sensory modalities, is our Self-perspective, also referred to in the literature as the first-person perspective (Vogeley and Fink, 2003). This perspective is defined by *what* we perceive and *how* we perceive it, as determined by the position and orientation of our body and head in space. The internal representation of this bodily position and orientation—referred to as the body-schema—is assumed to constitute the egocentric reference frame relative to which visuospatial judgments are made during Self-perspective judgments (SPJ) (Blanke, 2012, Moraresku and Vlcek, 2020, Vogeley et al., 2004, Zacks and Michelon, 2005). In contrast, visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) involves imagining and judging either *what* can be seen (level-1 VPT) or *how* a scene would appear (level-2 VPT) from Other-perspective—that is, a location and orientation in space different from one's own (Surtees et al., 2013). The present study focuses on level-2 SPJ and VPT. Throughout the manuscript, we use the abbreviation VPT to refer specifically to level-2 visuospatial perspective-taking.

Visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) incorporates diverse cognitive processes that are in part shared with SPJ. These shared processes are suggested to comprise visuospatial processing of a scene, executive functions, and even Theory of Mind (ToM) abilities, associated with social-cognitive reasoning about one's own or another's mental states (Gunia et al., 2021, Gunia et al., 2024, Seymour et al., 2018). Additionally, VPT reportedly requires specific processes such as mentally transforming one's Self-perspective into a target perspective. This has been shown to be based on one's body-schema (Kessler and Thomson 2010, Kessler and Rutherford, 2010) and other mental imagery processes required to imagine a visual scene from another perspective (Gunia et al., 2024, May, 2004, Zacks and Michelon, 2005, Michelon and

Zacks, 2006). Although most studies agree on the constituent functions of VPT, they emphasize different ones as the core component (e.g., May, 2004, Kessler and Thomson, 2010); however, various VPT tasks might require distinct functions with distinct intensity.

Self-perspective judgments (SPJ) is suggested to require less diversity of cognitive processes and previous behavioral results show that people spend more time during VPT than SPJ (David et al., 2006, Green et al., 2023, Gunia et al., 2024, Mazzarela et al., 2013). As VPT can be considered as a form of SPJ taken from an imagined perspective, they share many cognitive processes. However, few but still some processes specific to SPJ have been observed (Gunia et al., 2024), which might be related to the conscious awareness of one's spatial viewpoint as anchored to the body, often referred to as bodily Self-consciousness. SPJ is considered as part of the Self-consciousness (David et al., 2006, Vogeley et al., 2004), which is suggested to be developed through the process of comparing and distinguishing oneself from others (Rochat and Striano, 2000).

Both SPJ and VPT are integral to everyday cognition. Difficulties with VPT have been related to autism spectrum disorder (Hamilton et al., 2009), schizophrenia (Langdon et al., 2001), and aging (Inagaki et al., 2002). In all these cases, individuals are prone to respond from their Self-perspective, instead of responding from Other-perspective, showing an egocentric bias (for egocentric bias see Samson et al., 2010). It is generally accepted that taking Other-perspective is more cognitively demanding than representing one's own. While VPT research often focuses on improving performance in populations with VPT impairments, it may also be valuable to explore ways to reduce the gap between Other-perspective and Self-perspective judgments in the general population, enabling people to adopt another perspective as quickly and accurately as they make SPJs.

In our previous iEEG study using the same experiment but with different analysis methodology, provides a detailed description of the brain areas, and their timing in various types of processing required for VPT and SPJ (Gunia et al., 2024). Here we want to focus on one cognitive process that is hypothesized to be required both for Self- and Other-perspective judgments, namely processing the congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-perspective-related representations, i.e., differentiating the perspectives (De Meulemeester et al., 2021, Quesque and Brass, 2019, for related concept of Sensorimotor Interference, please see May, 2004). This process might be involved in both perspective judgments. However it should not be equally required for both, as viewing the world from the Self-perspective is our default state; therefore, distinguishing Other-related representations from the Self-perspective might be more effortful than the contrary (Tsakiris, 2017). Importantly, in our previous iEEG study we found in several brain areas an activity characterized by a very strong power increase to both SPJ and VPT judgments, but this power increase, additionally, was significantly stronger to VPT than to SPJ (Gunia et al., 2024). Considering its response profile, we named this processing VPT-prioritizing processing. Keeping in mind that effortful processing is related to

stronger brain activity (Taylor et al., 2014) and that one of those few brain areas exhibiting VPT-prioritizing processing was the Temporoparietal Junction (TPJ) (ROI PTPC in Gunia et al., 2024), an area traditionally related to Self-Other differentiation in ToM studies (Quesque and Brass, 2019, Sommer et al., 2007, van der Meer et al., 2011), we suggested that the observed very strong power increase in the TPJ area to both SPJ and VPT judgments but even stronger to VPT was the neural correlate of differentiating between Self- and Other-perspective-related representations. The onset of this VPT-prioritizing processing from the TPJ was starting early both in VPT and SPJ, which aligned with the suggestion that during VPT, processing the incongruence between multisensory representations related to Self- and Other-perspective happens at the beginning of the VPT (Kessler and Thomson, 2010).

Another important implication of finding VPT-prioritizing responses from the TPJ area was related to the SPJ condition. Of particular importance is the question, whether processing the representations related to Other-perspective happens during SPJ or not. Observing such a strong power of these VPT-prioritizing channels from the TPJ to the SPJ condition, let us suggest that observed response was the neural correlate of differentiating Self-and Other-perspective-related representation during SPJ.

The observed brain activity from the TPJ lasted very long both in VPT and SPJ. Considering this, we suggested that if VPT-prioritizing responses from the TPJ underpin processing the congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-perspective-related representations, then, in the first stage, this processing may be happening in both conditions. But, as distinguishing Other-related representations from Self-related representations may take more mental effort than vice versa (Tsakiris, 2017), the second stage of processing may happen only in the VPT condition, during which processing the congruences and incongruences between Self-and Other-related representations proceeds. On the other hand, in the SPJ condition, this processing could have been finalized in the first stage; therefore, the power modulation related to this process goes down. This may be the reason for the power difference between VPT and SPJ conditions captured by these channels (Gunia et al., 2024). However, in the literature, whether congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-perspective-related representations are processed during both perspective judgments remains an open question.

1.2 Processing the congruences and incongruences between Self and Other-related multisensory representations

May (2004) proposed that the increased difficulty of VPT compared to SPJ stems from the presence of multiple forms of incongruence between Self- and Other-perspectives. According to his update of the Sensorimotor Interference Hypothesis, this difficulty arises from a conflict between the actual spatial relations of objects in a scene—represented from the Self-perspective—and the imagined spatial relations of the same objects from the Other-

perspective. This interference depends on how incongruent these two spatial representations are. May (2004), based on the real-life Pointing Task, identified two primary sources of such interference: (1) **object direction disparity**, which refers to the difference in the perceived direction of an object from the Self versus Other-perspective, and (2) **head-direction disparity**, which occurs when Other-perspective requires a heading direction that differs from the actual one, causing interference between the imagined spatial reference frame and the egocentric reference frame centered on the actual head direction.

When specifying the subcomponents of these two sources of interference and outlining the ones present in various modern VPT tasks, we use the term **Congruence in multisensory representations between Self and Other** (for congruent and incongruent multisensory representations between Self and Other, see Quesque and Brass, 2019). We talk about multisensory representations because the Congruence effects described involve multiple sensory modalities of the human brain, including the visual, motor, somatosensory, and vestibular systems (for a review about multisensory perception, see Lewkowicz and Ghazanfar, 2009). Congruence in multisensory representations is defined specifically in relation to any Other-perspective. The Self-perspective in isolation does not invoke the notion of congruence, as congruence is a relational construct. It emerges only when at least one Other-perspective is introduced—whether it is an external viewpoint or an internally generated one, such as memory or imagination. In this sense, Other-perspective cannot be identical to Self-perspective and complete congruence is unattainable: even if the Other-perspective reflects one’s own memory, imagination, or is aligned at 0° angular disparity and within the same view plane (e.g., directly behind or in front of the participant), some degree of multisensory incongruence remains—for instance, in perceived body location or distance to an object. Therefore, two or more perspectives can be evaluated in terms of their degree of congruence or incongruence with one another.

In this paper, we concentrate only on one constituent part of Congruence in multisensory representations, which is left/right relation Congruence. However, the effect of Congruence in multisensory representations may refer to the extent to which variance in participants’ performance can be explained by the degree of congruence in representations between Self- and Other-perspectives across multiple sensory systems. For a hypothesis that the TPJ may be dealing with various incongruent representations between Self and Other, including multisensory ones, in a domain-general way, see Quesque and Brass, (2019). Depending on a the specific variant of the VPT task, and based on previous work (May 2004, Quesque and Brass 2019), we suggests that this Congruence in multisensory representations effect may be composed of multiple variables: **Congruence in left/right relation of objects** - Congruent when an object is, for example, to the left from both the Self- and Other-perspective (Fig. 1). This form of Congruence is the primary focus of the present paper. **Congruence in the angle of view** - Commonly referred to as Angular disparity in the VPT literature (e.g., Seymour

et al., 2018). Fully Congruent is when the target of transferring of the perspective (the VPT target angle) deviates from the Self-perspective with 0° . 180° is maximally Incongruent, with other angles falling between these extremes. For example, Fig. 1 shows a stimulus in which the Other-perspective is 90° Incongruent with the Self-perspective (for discussion, see Sections 1.3, 1.4, 4.1; for the analysis of this variable in our experiment, see Supplementary Section 2.3); **Congruence in distance** - Congruent when an object is at a similar distance from both perspectives. In our experiment, left/right Incongruent trials were more Congruent in distance than left/right Congruent trials, as the distance between the goal and the perspectives was more similar in the former (Fig. 1; for discussion, see Sections 1.3, 4.1; Supplementary Section 2.3); **Congruence in visibility** - Congruent when the same number of objects is visible from both perspectives. This applies mainly to level-1 VPT (for discussion, see Sections 1.3, 1.5, 4.2); **Congruence in appearance** - Congruent when an object appears similar (e.g., shape, size, orientation) from both perspectives (for discussion, see Sections 1.5, 4.2). **Congruence in the plane of view** - we suggest, drawing on May's object direction disparity concept (May, 2004), that Congruent stimulus does not require representing the Other-perspective in a different view plane from the Self-perspective. In our experiment, the Horizontal condition is Congruent in the view plane, whereas the Overhead condition is Incongruent because participants were instructed to imagine the scene in the Horizontal plane during VPT regardless of whether the stimulus was presented in the Horizontal or Overhead plane (Fig. 1; for the analysis of this variable in our experiment, see Supplementary Section 2.2). Other forms of Congruences in VPT studies are related to the body location, posture, or direction (e.g., Kessler and Thomson, 2010, May, 2004, Thiroux et al., 2010). Although we list these Congruences separately, their effects usually are so entangled that it is impossible to separate them. For example, Incongruence in the angle of view typically co-occurs with Incongruence in body direction; similarly, Incongruence in left/right relation is often accompanied by Incongruence in angle of view and body direction.

In this study, we focus on the left/right relation Congruence as the left/right judgments are one of the most frequent task of measuring VPT in recent years (Gunia et al., 2021) and because to our knowledge, it has not been documented that Other-perspective can be Congruent or Incongruent in left/right relation with Self-perspective on almost all angles other than 0° and 180° VPT target angles and this left/right Congruence affects participants performance.

1.3 Previous studies indicating on the effect of various types of Congruence in multisensory representations during VPT

Many VPT studies have tested various aspects of Congruence in multisensory representations; however, some have not been tested directly, though they may have contributed to the findings. First, the effect of left/right relation Congruence, the main focus of

this paper, may be hidden behind demands to mentally rotate one's body-schema toward the Other-perspective as angular disparity between the perspectives increases. For instance, in several studies, left/right Incongruence aligns with larger angular disparities, while smaller angular disparities are left/right Congruent (Kessler and Rutherford, 2010, Martin et al., 2020, Seymour et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016). Another study (May and Wendt, 2013) showed that identifying the left hand of a back-facing figure was easier than for a front-facing one. This finding may also indicate the effect of the left/right relation Congruence as the back-facing figure, when centered on the screen, shares the same left/right orientation as the participant. This highlights the importance of considering left/right relation Congruence as a distinct factor in VPT research.

Second, in a study by Kessler and Thomson (2010), similar to our experiment, conditions with greater angular disparity between Self- and Other-perspective, which were more difficult, also involved greater Incongruence in distance. Namely, in this study, the distance between a goal and the perspectives is more Congruent in low angular disparity conditions than in high angular disparity conditions. This again illustrates how different types of Congruence in multisensory representations can overlap—either reinforcing or counteracting one another—within VPT designs. Thus, it is essential to identify and discuss these constituent elements.

On the other hand, the effect of Congruence in visibility has been directly shown in level-1 VPT. Participants respond more slowly when judging how many dots an avatar sees if they themselves see a different number (Santiesteban et al., 2017, Schurz et al., 2025). In level-1 VPT studies, these egocentric errors—caused by interference from the Self-perspective—are often termed an explicit process, as individuals must deliberately inhibit their own perspective to correctly judge from another's view.

Overall, while the effect of certain types of Congruence in multisensory representations is not new to level-2 or level-1 VPT, there remains a gap in fully understanding its impact. It is still unclear whether, and how, other types of Congruence present in today's computer-based VPT tasks—such as left/right relation, distance, or view plane Congruence—contribute to Sensorimotor Interference hypothesis (May, 2004). In Section 1.2, building up on a previous work in the field (Quesque and Brass, 2019, May, 2004), we outlined various types of multisensory representations that can differ in Congruence between Self- and Other-perspectives and potentially influence results in popular computer-based VPT tasks. Therefore, these factors need to be discussed in VPT research.

1.4 Taking Other-perspective in the absence of another human-like figure

The VPT literature indicates that participants respond differently when perspective-taking involves a non-human-like stimulus instead of a human-like avatar. Experiments showed that removing the avatar slightly slowed responses, suggesting that a visible human figure—

especially in the same posture as the participant—may help compensate for multisensory incongruence between Self- and Other-perspectives (Michelon and Zacks, 2006, Kessler and Thomson, 2010).

To our knowledge, no study has explicitly tested the effect of left/right relation Congruence in the absence of a human-like figure. However, Michelon and Zacks (2006), while not directly addressing this question, reported that the 180° VPT target angle was the most challenging for participants—a finding that can be interpreted in light of left/right relation Congruence. In addition to other increased Incongruences in multisensory representations such as the angle of view, which potentially require greater mental transformation of one's body-schema, the 180° consistently produces left/right relation Incongruence between the Self- and Other-perspectives.

Demonstrating a left/right relation Congruence effect in the absence of an avatar would suggest that even in avatar-free tasks, VPT may engage social-cognitive processes, like Self–Other-related representations distinction. Specifically, it would imply that VPT judgments without another agent may not reduce to mere spatial reasoning between two objects but instead involve a distinction between Self- and externally anchored representations. When these representations are congruent, judgments are facilitated; when incongruent, performance declines. According to the criteria of the ToM tasks (Quesque and Rossetti, 2020), the engagement of these perspective-differentiation processes may thus align non-avatar VPT tasks with the criteria of ToM tasks and thus with social-cognitive reasoning.

1.5 The effect of Other-human-figure-related or non-related perspective on Self-perspective judgments

SPJ represents another pole of the perspectives judgment process. In SPJ, participants perform level-1 or level-2 judgments from within their own egocentric reference frame. Several level-1 perspective judgment studies show that incongruent Other-perspective-related representation—whether attributed to a human-like avatar or a non-human-like stimulus—can negatively impact SPJ performance (Samson and Apperly, 2010, Santiesteban et al., 2017). Based on the assumption that Self-perspective constitutes the default mode of perception (Vogel and Fink, 2003), processing information from an irrelevant Other-perspective—such as how many dots an avatar can see when participants are instructed to report their own view—was originally conceptualized as an Altercentric Interference (Samson and Apperly, 2010).

The Altercentric Interference can be seen as part of Congruence effect in multisensory representations. Here, rather than Self-related multisensory representations interfering with taking Other-perspective, the interference flows in the opposite direction: representations associated with the Other-perspective influence judgments from the Self-perspective. Particularly, this result of the avatar seeing different numbers of dots affecting SPJ (Samson and Apperly, 2010) illustrates the Congruence in visibility (see the Section 1.2).

Interestingly, Santiesteban et al. (2017) and Martin et al. (2019) demonstrated that participants were slower in SPJ when a non-human-like stimulus, such as an arrow or traffic light, was oriented toward fewer items than the participant could see, compared to when the counts were congruent. While these findings support the influence of Other-perspective-related representations on SPJ in the absence of a human figure-related stimulus, there remains a lack of studies examining this effect using abstract stimuli that carry no connotation of direction.

Compared to the level-1 perspective-judgments, the influence of Congruence in multisensory representations on SPJ during level-2 judgments yields more divergent findings. Martin et al. (2019), in one of their experiments, reported effects of various aspects of Congruence in multisensory representations on level-2 SPJ judgments, including conditions with and without avatar. On the other hand, Surtees et al. (2016) found no effect of Congruence in appearance on SPJ when SPJ and VPT trials were organized in separate blocks but observed this effect only when Self- and Other-perspectives were switching from trial to trial. None of these studies measured the Congruence in left/right relation on SPJ.

Thus, a gap remains in the perspective judgments literature regarding the effect of left/right relation Congruence between Self- and Other-perspectives on SPJ in general; and, particularly in tasks where the Other-perspective is defined by an abstract stimulus.

1.6 Motivation of the current study

To our knowledge, the effect of left/right relation Congruence has not been systematically studied in general — neither during VPT nor SPJ, regardless of experimental design. Moreover, we are not aware of any study that directly tests this effect using an experimental design that includes both types of trials: (1) trials where the object's left/right relation relative to the Other-perspective is Congruent with the Self-perspective not only at 0° or other low angular disparities, but also at higher angular disparities (excluding 180°); and (2) trials where this relation is Incongruent not only at 180° or other high angular disparities, but also at lower angular disparities (excluding 0°) (see Fig. 1).

Finding iEEG brain responses exhibiting strong, early, and long response profiles to both VPT and SPJ conditions and being even stronger in VPT than in SPJ in the brain area that is widely related to distinguishing between Self-and Other-related representations (TPJ), motivated this current study. To examine whether participants were indeed processing congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-related representations during both SPJ and VPT judgments, we analyzed their behavioral responses. Specifically, we separated trial-types in the SPJ and VPT conditions based on whether the left/right relation of a target object was the same from both perspectives (Congruent) or conflicting (Incongruent). Our rationale was that if participants process the congruence between perspectives during both types of judgments, they would show distinct behavioral responses to Incongruent compared to

Congruent trials in both conditions. While we acknowledge that the data come from patients with epilepsy (see Study Limitations, Section 4.5), we suggest that the observed effects may generalize to the neurotypical population and are not a by-product of epilepsy (see Supplementary Results and Analysis, Section 2.1). Importantly, by presenting these findings, we aim to highlight key variables for future VPT studies in neurotypical individuals.

1.7 Hypotheses of the current study

The aim of this study was to test the hypothesis that the cognitive process of processing the congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-perspective, i.e., differentiating the perspectives, happens in both Self- and Other-perspective judgments.

Under this hypothesis, we expected the following results. First, we expected the Incongruence in left/right relation of an object between participants' Self-perspective and Other-perspective to negatively affect participants' performance to take Other-perspective, even when we have this Incongruence on almost all angles of the target perspective. Second, based on the previous study (Gunia et al. 2024), we expected the Incongruence in left/right relation of the object between participants' Self-perspective and Other-perspective to negatively affect participants' performance to respond from Self-perspective, even when this perspective does not visually belong to another human-like agent but is related to an abstract stimulus.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

This behavioral dataset was collected alongside intracranial EEG (iEEG) recordings, as the original main aim of the study was to characterize the temporal and anatomical profiles of brain processes involved in VPT and SPJ. Because iEEG is an invasive method, the data were necessarily collected from patients undergoing clinical intracranial monitoring for pharmacoresistant epilepsy at the Motol Epilepsy Center in Prague, Czech Republic. Please, see Study Limitations, Section 4.5 and Supplementary Section 2.1 for why we consider the behavioral results presented here apply to the general population. We recorded the iEEG and behavioral data from this experiment from 29 participants (20 women, median age 28, range 18–48, 28 right-handed, education level: two - primary school, 22 - secondary school, five - college). The iEEG data from these participants, collected during the same experiment, along with the behavioral data analyzed using a different methodological approach, are reported elsewhere (Gunia et al., 2024). All patients underwent intracranial EEG (iEEG) monitoring and stereo-encephalography using stereotactically implanted multi-contact electrodes for the clinical purpose of localizing seizure onset zones. Electrode implantation sites were determined strictly according to clinical indications. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of

Motol University Hospital, and all participants voluntarily provided written informed consent. All had normal or corrected-to-normal vision.

2.2. Visuospatial perspective-taking task

The visual perspective-taking (VPT) task employed in this study was developed using Unreal Editor (UT 2004, EpicGames, Raleigh, NC, 2004) and adapted from the Arena Perspective-Taking Task (APTT; Marková et al., 2015) to measure both VPT and SPJ. The task presented participants with a series of static scenes depicting a virtual circular arena, each containing a green landmark —comprising three vertical bars—placed on the arena wall, and a red circular goal positioned on the arena floor (Fig. 1). Scenes were rendered in either overhead (Overhead) or horizontal (Horizontal) view. In Overhead, the goal occupied 15% of the arena diameter; in Horizontal, it was 7%. In both views, the goal was placed either 25° to the left or right of the landmark's location (defined relative to the center of the arena) and at a distance of 16% of the arena diameter from the wall. Stimuli were presented on a 15.6-inch TFT notebook monitor. The visual angles subtended by the images were 12 × 6 degrees (horizontal × vertical) in the Overhead condition and 10 × 7 degrees in the Horizontal condition. The task was implemented and data collected using the PsychoPy 1.84 software package (Peirce et al., 2019).

The landmark appeared at eight equidistant degrees along the arena wall: 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135° (counter-clockwise trials), and 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315° (clockwise trials), defined relative to the participant's Self-perspective in the Horizontal condition (with 0° located behind the participant and 180° directly in front), and relative to the bottom of the display in the Overhead condition. In the Horizontal condition, the landmark at 0° was occluded, and participants were instructed to imagine it behind them. The participants were asked to press the left/right arrow keys on a keyboard if the goal was to the left/right, respectively. They responded either from their visuospatial perspective in the **SPJ condition** or imagined themselves standing at the landmark's position, facing the arena center, and estimated the goal's left/right location from the imagined perspective in the **VPT condition** (Fig. 1). Each of the eight landmark degrees appeared 16 times in both Overhead and Horizontal conditions (eight with the goal on the left, eight on the right), resulting in 32 unique scene combinations. Landmark order was pseudo-randomized and fixed across participants. The task originally employed a 2 × 2 design crossing View (Overhead vs. Horizontal) with Perspective (SPJ vs. VPT). Each image was presented for 1500 ms followed by a 1500 ms black screen with a cross in the center. The participants were reminded to respond quickly, as the time to view the picture was limited to 1500 ms and the time to respond to 3000 ms (Participants could respond during the 1500 ms of the stimulus presentation and the following 1500 ms of the central cross presentation). Firstly, there was a training period of 16 trials, in which the participants received feedback about their response accuracy. There was no feedback in the following 256 test trials. The experiment lasted about 30 minutes and consisted of 256 test trials divided into four

sessions. Each session consisted of four blocks containing 16 trials (64 in total), with SPJ and VPT presented in either the Overhead or Horizontal view in separate blocks. The order of blocks in the sessions was counterbalanced, with a pause between them of subject-controlled length.

For the purpose of the current study, we distinguished trials based on the Congruence in the left/right relation of the goal relative to Self- and Other-perspective (green landmark). Considering the left/right location of the goal relative to the green landmark on each degree and Self-perspective, there were left/right Congruent and Incongruent trial-types. In the Congruent trial-type, the correct response from the SPJ and VPT was the same (Fig. 1). These were all trials where the landmark was presented at a 0° . Also, Congruent were those counterclockwise degree trials, where the goal was presented to the right side from both perspectives and those clockwise degree trials, where the goal was presented to the left side from both perspectives. Theoretically, in the Congruent trial-type, participants could perform correctly even without distinguishing between perspectives. On the contrary, in the Incongruent trials, the correct response from each perspective was distinct; here, participants needed to differentiate between Self- and Other-perspectives to perform correctly. Incongruent were all 180° trials, all counterclockwise degree trials with the goal to the left from the landmark but to the right from the Self-perspective, and all clockwise trials with the goal to the right from the landmark but to the left from the Self-perspective (Fig. 1). Out of all 256 trials, 128 were left/right relation Congruent and 128 Incongruent trials.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the visuospatial perspective-taking task. The arena scene was displayed on a computer screen either in an overhead view (Overhead condition) (**a. Top panel**) or a horizontal view (Horizontal condition) (**a. Bottom panel**). In the SPJ condition, participants responded based on their own visuospatial perspective. In the VPT condition, they were instructed to imagine themselves standing at the landmark’s location, facing the center of the arena, and to judge the red goal’s left/right location from that imagined perspective. In both SPJ and VPT conditions, half of the trials featured the same left/right relation from both perspectives (Congruent) (**a. Right panel**)—while in the other half, the relation was reversed (Incongruent) (**a. Left panel**). **Section b** shows the temporal structure of the trials. Participants could respond via button press either during the 1500 ms of stimulus presentation or during the subsequent 1500 ms when the central fixation cross was shown. For illustration

purposes, arrows and text have been added to the images, and the goal is displayed in a brighter color.

(For original images used in the experiment, see

https://osf.io/wuapg/?view_only=8044ddd9cb35438e84e84e9f663e16c40)

2.3 Statistical analysis

To estimate the participants' performance in the VPT task, we measured the participants' response times (RT) and mean correct responses (Accuracy) in Congruent and Incongruent SPJ and VPT conditions. From the RT and Accuracy analysis we rejected the data of those participants who did not perform any experimental session (group of four blocks, with 64 trials in total) above 75% correct. Additionally, considering that this behavioral data was recorded from patients with epilepsy during iEEG monitoring, we excluded from the behavioral analysis those trials in which participants exhibited multiple interictal epileptiform discharges (IEDs), in order to avoid misinterpreting RT or Accuracy measures that may have been affected by frequent epileptic activity. To detect these trials, we applied the automatic IED detector developed by Janca et al. (2015) on the iEEG data of the participants, similar to previous iEEG studies (Gunia et al., 2024, Moraresku et al., 2023, Moraresku et al., 2025, Vlcek et al., 2020). To ensure accurate identification of IED-marked trials, we visually inspected the corresponding iEEG data using the FieldTrip toolbox (Oostenveld et al., 2011) and excluded these trials from the behavioral analysis.

We compared participants' mean Accuracy and RTs in the conditions of interest using the linear mixed-effects model (LMM) analysis (Field et al., 2012, Steele, 2008) in R statistical software (R Core Team, 2013), using lme4 package (Bates et al., 2003) and the p-values were obtained via lmerTest (Kuznetsova et al., 2013). The LMM analyses used Satterthwaite approximation method (Luke, 2017) with maximum likelihood (ML) estimation as ML enables model comparison and is appropriate when the hypothesis is about a fixed effect (Field et al., 2012). Estimated marginal means and pairwise comparisons were computed using the emmeans package (Lenth et al., 2025) in R, with degrees of freedom estimated via the Satterthwaite approximation. Pairwise comparisons were adjusted for multiple testing using Tukey's method.

As the primary focus of this study was the effect of left/right Congruence during Self- and Other-perspective judgments, we constructed LMMs with Perspective and left/right Congruence as fixed effects. To account for participant-level variability, we included Participant as a random factor and to find the best-fit model between random intercept and random slope models for Congruence, we used ANOVA (Field et al., 2012, Steele, 2008).

3. Results

We conducted the LMM analysis on the data of the 26 participants. Three participants were excluded from the final analysis, due to incorrect or missing responses, and a high number of IED-marked trials, resulting in fewer than 75% usable trials in each of the four sessions. To analyze the Accuracy data, we used LMM. The best-fit model was Accuracy \sim Congruence * Perspective + (1 + Congruence | ParticipantID). The fixed effects were Congruence (Congruent, Incongruent) and Perspective (SPJ VPT), including their interaction. The model also included Participant as a random effect, with random slopes for Congruence per participant. The results revealed a significant fixed effect of Congruence at the reference level SPJ ($b = 0.04419$, $SE = 0.01873$, $t(36.45) = -2.359$, $p = 0.0238$). Consistent with this, the difference between the marginal means of Congruence, averaged over both levels of Perspective, was also significant ($b = 0.0557$, $SE = 0.0173$, $t(26.4) = 3.227$, $p = 0.0033$). Participants made significantly more errors on Incongruent trials compared to Congruent ones, in both the Self and VPT conditions (Fig. 1a). The effect of Perspective was not significant either at the reference level Congruent trials or when comparing its marginal means averaged over both levels of Congruence. The interaction between Congruence and Perspective was also not significant. This result is consistent with previous finding using the same dataset but a different analysis approach: when Congruent and Incongruent trials were not separated, there was no significant difference in Accuracy between SPJ and VPT (Gunia et al., 2024).

The RT analysis with the best fit LMM model RT \sim Congruence * Perspective + (1 | ParticipantID) on the participants' responses only from the correct trials showed the significant fixed effects of Congruence at the reference level SPJ ($b = -0.04154$, $SE = 0.01324$, $t(5216.45) = -3.14$, $p = 0.0017$), Perspective at the reference level Congruent trials ($b = 0.22471$, $SE = 0.01312$, $t(5216.22) = 17.13$, $p < 0.001$), and the significant interaction between these factors ($b = 0.13276$, $SE = 0.01885$, $t(5216.24) = 7.04$, $p < 0.001$). Post hoc analysis showed that participants were slower in the Incongruent VPT condition than in Congruent ($b = -0.0912$, $SE = 0.0134$, $t(5216) = -6.796$, $p < 0.0001$). Contrary, in the SPJ condition, they were faster in Incongruent compared to the Congruent condition (Fig. 1b). Also, consistent with the previous result (Gunia et al., 2024), participants were faster in SPJ compared to the VPT condition across both levels of Congruence ($b = -0.291$, $SE = 0.00942$, $t(5216) = -30.892$, $p < 0.0001$).

As we write in the Methods section 2.2, the 0° and 180° trials differed from the other trial-types. At 0°, both the SPJ and VPT conditions included only left/right Congruent trials, while at 180°, both conditions included only left/right Incongruent trials. To test whether the effect of left/right relation Congruence on Accuracy and RTs held without these two trial-types, we re-ran the analysis excluding the 0° and 180° trials. Using the same LMM model as in the full analysis, the Accuracy model again showed a significant fixed effect of Congruence at the reference level SPJ ($b = -0.04644$, $SE = 0.01733$, $t(43.70) = -2.680$, $p = 0.0103$). When averaged over both levels of Perspective, participants made more errors on Incongruent compared to

Congruent trials in both SPJ and VPT conditions ($b = 0.0511$, $SE = 0.0153$, $t(26.7) = 3.334$, $p = 0.0025$) (see Supplementary Fig. 1a). No other effects or interactions were significant.

For RT analysis excluding the 0° and 180° trials, we again considered only correct responses. The same model as in the full analysis, showed significant fixed effects of Congruence at the reference level SPJ ($b = -0.07461$, $SE = 0.01477$, $t(3935.51) = -5.051$, $p < 0.0001$) and Perspective at the reference level Congruent trials ($b = 0.23538$, $SE = 0.01455$, $t(3935.33) = 16.177$, $p < 0.0001$), as well as a significant interaction between them ($b = 0.08433$, $SE = 0.02091$, $t(3935.35) = 4.033$, $p < 0.0001$). Participants responded faster on Incongruent than on Congruent trials in SPJ. For VPT condition, the pattern was similar to the full analysis—slower RTs in Incongruent than Congruent trials—but the post hoc analysis did not show significance (see Supplementary Fig. 1b). As in the previous analysis, when averaged over both levels of Congruence, responses in the SPJ condition were overall faster than in the VPT condition ($b = -0.278$, $SE = 0.0105$, $t(3935) = -26.554$, $p < 0.0001$).

To examine whether the observed left/right relation Congruence was not driven by below-norm performance on intelligence tests potentially related to epilepsy, we repeated the analyses on a subset of participants who scored within the normative range on intelligence and visuospatial scales. In the supplementary analysis (Supplementary section 2.1), we excluded eight participants who scored below the normal range. The accuracy results for the remaining 18 participants were unchanged, and the RT results showed a similar pattern. For a detailed rationale as to why we consider that the results of the behavioral data presented here—despite being collected from patients with epilepsy— may apply to the general population and provide valuable insights as the future direction of the VPT and SPJ studies in neurotypical subjects, please, see the Study limitations, section 4.5.

Fig. 2. Mean accuracy and response times for left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials during VPT and SPJ. **Section a** shows percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for left/right Congruent (Cong, blue) and Incongruent (Incong, pink) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). The black asterisk (*) denotes significant difference between Congruent and Incongruent trials. Participants were more correct in Congruent compared to Incongruent trials during both VPT and SPJ. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. The black asterisk denotes significant difference between the left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials and the red one - significant difference between VPT and SPJ. In VPT, participants were faster in Congruent than Incongruent trials, while in SPJ, the opposite pattern emerged. Participants were faster in SPJ compared to VPT.

4. Discussion

This behavioral study was driven by a gap in the perspective-taking literature regarding the role of left/right relation Congruence in Self- and Other-perspective judgments and our previous iEEG work (Gunia et al., 2024). In the iEEG data from the VPT experiment, we observed early, sustained, and strong power modulation in a brain region commonly associated with distinguishing various Self- and Other-related representations in ToM research (Quesque and Brass, 2019). This modulation was present in both Self- and Other-perspective judgments (i.e., SPJ and VPT) but was stronger in the latter, consistent with the idea that distinguishing Other-related representations from Self-related ones in VPT is more cognitively demanding than the reverse (Tsakiris, 2017). It motivated the current study in two ways. Firstly, observing this brain activity in a VPT experiment gave hints about the domain-general function of the temporoparietal junction (TPJ) in processing Incongruences between various Self- and Other-related representations (Quesque and Brass, 2019). Secondly, observing it not only during Other-perspective judgments but also during SPJ, suggested that Incongruences in Other-related representations could be processed even during SPJ judgments.

To further explore this question, we re-analyzed the behavioral responses of the same participants from the iEEG study using a novel analysis approach to examine whether Congruence and Incongruence between perspectives were processed differently. Specifically, we categorized trial-types based on the Congruence in left/right relation between the Self- and Other-perspective.

We aimed to determine whether these behavioral responses would differ according to left/right Congruence or Incongruence, both when judging from the Self-perspective and when adopting the Other-perspective—providing further motivation to investigate corresponding differences in their neural responses. Although the behavioral data presented here come from patients with epilepsy (see Study limitations, section 4.5, and Supplementary materials, section 2.1), they highlight an overlooked factor in VPT research that significantly impacts task performance and offers a possibility for addressing longstanding questions in VPT, SPJ, and broader Theory of Mind research.

Our experiment demonstrated that incongruence between Self- and Other-perspectives—specifically regarding the left/right spatial relation of a target object—negatively impacts participants' performance in both Other- and Self-perspective judgments (Fig. 2). First, and in agreement with our first hypothesis, we show that the mere presence of a left/right Incongruent Self-perspective diminishes accuracy when participants respond from the Other-perspective. This effect was also evident in the reaction times (RTs) of correct responses (Fig. 2b). When we excluded the 0° (always Congruent) and 180° (always Incongruent) trials from the RT analysis, the trend persisted in the VPT condition (slower responses in Incongruent trials), although the difference was no longer statistically significant (Supplementary Fig. 1b). These accuracy and RT findings show that left/right Incongruence between Self- and Other-perspectives impairs the process of adopting the Other-perspective.

Next, confirming our second hypothesis, we found that the mere presence of a left/right Incongruent Other-perspective—even when this perspective was not related to a human-like agent and the task did not require from trial to trial perspective switching — impairs accuracy during Self-perspective judgments in a level-2 VPT task (Fig. 2a). However, participants were faster to respond from the Self-perspective in Incongruent compared to Congruent trials (Fig. 2b). We interpret this RT finding with caution, as it may be confounded by the proximity of the goal to the mid-line of the arena in some trials (e.g., 135° and 225°), complicating the left/right SPJ more in Congruent than in Incongruent trials (Supplementary Fig. 2b). This interpretation is supported by the accuracy data showing the trend that on the same degrees, participants were either slightly more accurate or equally accurate in SPJ during Incongruent versus Congruent trials (Supplementary Fig. 2a).

In the following section, we discuss these findings in the context of existing research on VPT, SPJ, and more broadly, Theory of Mind.

4.1 The effect of left/right relation Congruence on taking Other-visuospatial perspective

In the VPT literature, various types of multisensory congruences have been studied, but the effect of the left/right relation Congruence on taking Other-perspective has been largely overlooked. Some previous studies included left/right relation Congruence in their

experimental designs, but did not test its effect directly. In those designs, left/right Incongruent trials typically aligned with more demanding higher VPT target angles, while Congruent trials aligned with easier lower angles (Kessler and Rutherford, 2010, Martin et al., 2020, Seymour et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016).

Here, we tested the effect of the left/right relation Congruence. In contrast, to above referred studies, our experiment includes trials where the left/right relation of an object relative to the Other-perspective matches the Self-perspective (i.e., is Congruent) not only at 0° or other low angles, but also at higher angles—excluding 180°. Likewise, it includes trials where the left/right relation is opposite (Incongruent) not only at 180° or other high VPT target angles, but also at lower angles—excluding 0°.

By pooling Congruent versus Incongruent trials across various angles, in line with our hypothesis, our results reveal that participants' accuracy is affected by whether left/right judgments from Self- and Other-perspectives are Congruent or not (Fig. 2). Participants made fewer errors when the Other-perspective was Congruent in left/right relation with their own, and more errors when the perspectives differed. This demonstrates that even in the absence of a significant overall accuracy difference between Self and VPT conditions, the two perspectives still influence each other's response accuracy.

Building on our previous iEEG findings (Gunia et al., 2024), the observation that participants showed different behavioral performance in Congruent versus Incongruent VPT trials—specifically, that Incongruent left/right representation with Self-perspective interfered with VPT—provided support for our interpretation (based on previous work of another group - Quesque and Brass, 2019) that early, sustained, and robust TPJ responses may reflect the differentiation between Self-and Other-related representations. This motivates the future direction of our research to compare brain activity in left/right Congruent versus Incongruent trials in the iEEG data to further test this hypothesis.

In this paper, we do not argue that Congruence in the angle of view does not affect VPT performance. This effect has been demonstrated in earlier studies, such as Kessler and Thomson (2010), where both smaller and higher VPT target angle conditions included both Congruent or Incongruent left/right relation trials. Our supplementary analysis also shows that participants make more errors and are slower in the higher VPT target angle trials (Supplementary Analysis and Results Section 2.3). However, as in Kessler and Thomson (2010), in our experiment, Congruence in distance potentially adds-up to the angle effect: higher VPT target angle trials were also more Incongruent in distance than lower. The main argument of this paper concerning Other-perspective judgment is that the left/right relation Congruence is an important factor in taking the Other-perspective and it deserves attention in VPT research. First, it influences response accuracy, showing that Self-related representations are processed during Other-perspective judgments—where congruent representations facilitate, and incongruent ones interfere with successful VPT. Second, measuring the effect of left/right

Congruence in VPT neuroimaging studies may offer insights into the proposed domain-general role of the TPJ in processing diverse Self- and Other-related representations (Quesque and Brass, 2019).

Hereby, we emphasize the importance of designing experiments that, where possible, separate different types of Congruence in multisensory representations. For example, left/right Incongruence does not necessarily coincide with greater Incongruence in angle of view or distance, and left/right Congruence does not always correspond to lower Incongruence in these dimensions. At the same time, we acknowledge that sometimes various Congruences in multisensory representations may be inseparable. In our experiment as well, in 0° trials, the goal is always left/right Congruent and Congruent in distance (i.e., close from both Self- and imagined perspectives), while 180° trials are always left/right Incongruent and Incongruent in distance (i.e., far from Self-perspective, close from Other-perspective). Across intermediate angles clockwise and counter-clockwise—Low Degree (45°), Middle Degree (90°), and High Degree (135°)—the effects of angle of view Congruence and left/right relation Congruence remain interdependent. Low Degree trials are generally more Congruent in distance than High Degree trials, so distance Congruence adds to angle Congruence. However, within Low and High Degrees, left/right Congruent trials tend to be less Congruent in distance than left/right Incongruent trials, creating opposing influences. As a result, distance Congruence can amplify the angle Congruence effect while attenuating the left/right Congruence effect. In the Supplementary analysis, we report the effect of these angles during VPT and SPJ (Supplementary section 2.3).

A similar interdependence is observed between the left/right Congruence and the view plane (Overhead or Horizontal condition). For instance, in Horizontal trials, left/right Congruent trials at both Low and High Degrees appear more Incongruent in distance than in Overhead trials, as the goal appears farther from the Self-perspective. In the Supplementary analysis, we report the effect of the view plane during VPT and SPJ (Supplementary section 2.2).

Additionally, their potential conceptual interdependence should be considered, as they may be processed by the TPJ in a domain-general manner (Quesque and Brass, 2019). This view is supported by evidence of increased TPJ activity across various tasks requiring distinguishing Congruent and Incongruent Self- and Other-related multisensory and even higher-level cognitive representations (e.g., beliefs). Overall, these multisensory Congruences may be conceptually and statistically so intertwined that their effects are impossible to fully disentangle.

Lastly, we demonstrate the effect of left/right relation Congruence with the Self-perspective during VPT in the absence of an avatar. This may suggest the inherently social nature of VPT judgments (Baron-Cohen, 1995, Miller, 2022) in our task, even though no other agent was present. Specifically, when participants are explicitly instructed to assign a perspective to an abstract stimulus, apparently, instead of a mere spatial comparison between

that stimulus and the goal, there happens a Theory of Mind judgment. If the Congruence or Incongruence of the Self-perspective alters how participants estimate the spatial relation between the abstract stimulus and the goal, it implies a differentiation between the Self-related and the abstract stimulus-related representations. When these representations are congruent, the task becomes easier; when they are incongruent, it becomes more difficult. According to the criteria of ToM tasks (Quesque and Rossetti, 2020), the involvement of differentiation between Self and Other-related representations may align VPT tasks without an avatar with ToM tasks, and therefore with social-cognitive reasoning.

4.2 The effect of left/right relation Congruence on Self-perspective judgments

In line with our expectation, driven by the previous iEEG findings (Gunia et al., 2024), our results show that participants make more errors in judging the left/right relation of an object from their Self-perspective when the task-irrelevant Other-perspective has an Incongruent left/right relation. This supports our hypothesis that processing of the congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-perspective occurs even during Self-perspective judgments. Broadly, it fits with the idea that being consciously aware of one's own Self-perspective is part of the Self-consciousness (David et al., 2006, Vogeley et al., 2004), which may be developed through the process of distinguishing oneself from others (Rochat and Striano, 2000).

Observing the Congruence effect on the SPJ in the behavioral data of our participants provided support for the previous interpretation that early, sustained, and robust TPJ responses to SPJ condition observed in the iEEG data of these participants (Gunia et al., 2024), which was also present in VPT, may reflect the differentiation between Self-and Other-related representations and that this process is present not only during taking another perspective but also when responding from the Self-perspective. Following this result, to further test this hypothesis, we plan to compare brain activity in left/right Congruent versus Incongruent trials in the SPJ condition in the iEEG data.

To our knowledge this is a first account showing the left/right relation Congruence effect on Self-perspective judgments. Previous studies (Samson and Apperly, 2010, Santiesteban et al., 2017) reported that an avatar's incongruent visibility of dots negatively affects SPJ performance in level-1 perspective-taking tasks—a phenomenon termed the Altercentric Interference Effect (Samson and Apperly, 2010). Another study (Surtees et al., 2016) found that this effect consistently occurs in Level-1 SPJ, but in Level-2 SPJ, it emerges only when Self- and Other-perspective judgments alternate from trial to trial, not when presented in separate blocks.

Here we show the Altercentric Interference Effect, which we discuss in this paper as the constituent part of the Congruence effect in multisensory representations, on level-2 SPJ

judgments, where VPT and SPJ were organized in different blocks. Namely, we show that a task-irrelevant Other-perspective impacts the accuracy of judgments about an object's left/right relation from the Self-perspective even when there is no need to rapidly switch perspectives between trials. Other than seeing this observation in patients with epilepsy and not in neurotypical subjects as in other studies (see Study limitations, section 4.5 and Supplementary materials, section 2.1), our contrasting finding to Surtees et al., 2016 might be due to the specificity of the task. Unlike the presented task by us, which required left/right judgments, Surtees et al., 2016 used a task asking whether a number was seen as a '6' or a '9' from Self- and Other-perspective. Although both of the tasks require level-2 judgments, considering the specificity of the tasks, most likely, they employ different aspects of Congruence effect in multisensory representations with different intensity. Namely, Surtees et al., (2016) experiment probably employs with the most intensity the Congruence in appearance as the correct response depends on how the stimulus appears from Self-perspective. On the other hand, our experiment, in addition to Congruence in appearance, also employs Congruence in distance and the most importantly - Congruence in left/right relation. Moreover, left/right judgments are more directly tied to body-schema and likely engage somatosensory representations more than number appearance tasks.

Importantly, our experiment showed the effect of the left/right relation Congruence on Self-perspective judgments in the absence of another human-like figure. This partially contrasts with Samson and Apperly's (2010) findings on the Altercentric Interference effect in level-1 judgments, as they suggested it may be limited to Other-perspectives specifically associated with a human-like agent. In one of their experiments, Samson and Apperly tested level-1 perspective judgments using Congruent and Incongruent visibility judgments. Instead of an avatar, they used a rectangle in some conditions—a stimulus similar to ours, lacking explicit directionality. In these conditions, they found no effect of visibility Congruence on RTs. However, in the same experiment, when an avatar was used (viewing either the same or a different number of dots as the participant), they observed slower responses. In terms of accuracy, no Congruence in visibility effect was found for SPJ, whether the stimulus was an avatar or a rectangle.

One of the explanations for the contrast between their findings and ours—besides the fact that the data come from patients with epilepsy and the difference in task—is that their study used only SPJ. As a result, participants could likely ignore the rectangle, which was not explicitly tied to an Other-perspective by the task design. In contrast, our experiment, while also using an abstract stimulus, explicitly linked it to the Other-perspective by having the VPT condition, in a different block but in the same experiment. This design meant that, although participants were not required to switch perspective from trial to trial, they were explicitly instructed and trained to associate a visuospatial perspective with the abstract stimulus. This awareness that the abstract stimulus represented the Other-perspective likely explains why, in

our experiment, the Incongruent perspective linked to the abstract stimulus interfered with Self-perspective judgments.

Other studies have demonstrated Congruence in the visibility effect in level-1 Self-perspective judgments using non-human directional cues such as arrows, lamps, or traffic lights facing different numbers of dots than the participant (Santiesteban et al., 2017, Martin et al., 2019). What makes our findings novel is that even with an abstract, non-directional stimulus, the irrelevant Other-perspective influenced participants' left/right judgments during level-2 SPJ with a block experimental design. Even though the data come from the patients with epilepsy, this emphasizes the importance of further investigating the role of left/right relation Congruence in level-2 SPJ in the general population.

Overall, demonstrating the effect of left/right relation Congruence with the Other-perspective during SPJ, in the absence of an avatar, further supports the ToM nature of visuospatial perspective judgments tasks that do not involve another agent beyond the participant. It shows that even without a human-like figure, when participants are aware of the abstract stimulus-related perspective, the task goes beyond a simple spatial judgment between the Self and a goal. If Congruent and Incongruent Other-perspectives—linked to an abstract stimulus—differentially affect the perceived spatial relation between the Self and the goal, it implies that participants distinguish between Self-related and abstract stimulus-related representations. This positions those SPJ tasks involving another perspective—even if tied to an abstract stimulus—within the scope of ToM tasks (Quesque and Rossetti, 2020).

4.4 The implications of the observed left/right relation Congruence effect on the accuracy of taking Self and Other visuospatial perspective for the Theory of Mind research

Finding the left/right relation Congruence effect on the accuracy of both Other-perspective and Self-perspective judgments brings the cognitive processes underlying visuospatial perspective judgments closer to those involved in other ToM tasks (Quesque and Brass, 2019). In the social cognition literature (e.g., Baron-Cohen, 1995, Miller, 2022), VPT is described as a part of ToM—a broad concept incorporating various cognitive processes involved in reasoning on Self and Other-related mental states. One such process is Belief Reasoning (BR), which, like VPT, is thought to involve the cognitive mechanisms necessary for genuine ToM tasks (Quesque and Rossetti, 2020). Namely, ToM tasks incorporate attributing a mental state to others by distinguishing between their own and others' mental states, or distinguishing between their own actual and imagined mental states. If one's own and another's mental states are incongruent, in order to attribute mental states to another agent, one is required to inhibit the irrelevant Self-related mental state and give priority to the relevant Other-related one. When the Self- and Other-related mental states are matching, there is no need for inhibition of the Self-mental state (Quesque and Rossetti, 2020). Thus, it is

evident that this need to inhibit a Self-incongruent mental state introduces more challenges in ToM tasks than scenarios where no such inhibition is required.

The role of congruence has long been studied in BR research. False Belief Reasoning (FBR) vs. True Belief Reasoning (TBR) paradigms inherently manipulate congruence: in FBR, the participant's and the agent's beliefs are incongruent, while in TBR, they are congruent (Green et al., 2023, Sommer et al., 2018, van der Meer et al., 2011). These studies show that reasoning about another's belief is more difficult in the incongruent (FBR) condition. One explanation is interference from the incongruent Self-belief (but see Rahman et al., 2021 - for the confounding explanations of this effect). Similarly, in VPT, taking another's visuospatial perspective supposedly requires distinguishing it from one's own. When the perspectives are incongruent, inhibition of one's own visuospatial representation and prioritization of the Other-perspective is required. However, when they are congruent—at least on the response-relevant dimension, such as left/right spatial relation—this inhibition is unnecessary. In our study, the Congruent left/right relation in the VPT task meant that participants' Self-perspective matched the Other-perspective on the correct response dimension. We suggest that the higher error rate in Incongruent left/right VPT conditions compared to Congruent is the result of interference from the Incongruent Self-perspective. This indicates the possible similar underlying cognitive mechanisms among VPT and BR - processing incongruences between Self and Other-related representations, which as suggested by Quesque and Brass (2019) may be dealt in a domain-general manner by similar brain processes.

Moreover, our results about the Self-perspective judgments being more erroneous when being Incongruent with Other-perspective is also in agreement with BR findings about Self-beliefs. For instance, studies by Speiger et al. (2025) and van der Wel et al. (2014) show that participants struggle more to report their own beliefs when they conflict with another agent's belief. These results show that it is not only that, for participants, just responding from their own default visuospatial perspective or responding about their own belief is easier than responding about another's belief or perspective, but these Self-perspective or Self-belief judgments are easier when they are congruent with another's perspective and belief. This suggests that even though representing Self-perspective and beliefs is our default state, still, in the presence of an Other-related perspective or belief, there is processing of the congruences and incongruences between one's own and Other-related representations, and the congruent representations ease the process of making Self-belief and Self-perspective judgments.

Overall, our current findings from Self- and Other-visuospatial judgments are in line with the suggestion that the Congruence effect in Self- and Other-related representations may reflect a common process underlying Self–Other visuospatial perspective and belief judgments, and that computing congruences and incongruences between Self- and Other-beliefs can be one of the modalities of these representations—not a sensory modality, but a cognitive one. (Quesque and Brass 2019). This possible intersection in the cognitive mechanisms underlying

Self-Other perspective and belief judgments could be used to find ways to improve understanding and judgment about various Self- and Other-related representations.

4.5 Study limitations and future directions

This study has several limitations. First, the data were collected from patients with epilepsy, and we do not have comparable data from neurotypical participants. However, as noted in the Introduction and Hypotheses sections 1, this analysis is a follow-up to the previous iEEG study (Gunia et al., 2024), which showed trends to address long-standing questions in VPT research. To further explore these questions and inform future directions, we conducted a novel behavioral analysis. Although we are cautious in generalizing to the neurotypical population, the performance of the participants aligns with results from other VPT studies involving neurotypical individuals, suggesting similar trends may apply.

In a prior analysis using the same dataset—without separating Congruent and Incongruent left/right trials—the performance across Self- and Other-perspective conditions were compared (Gunia et al., 2024). The participants' RT results aligned with those of neurotypical subjects in other studies contrasting VPT and SPJ (David et al., 2006, Mazzarella et al., 2013), and their accuracy results were also similar to neurotypical performance in a previous study (David et al., 2006). Overall, the participants showed high performance in both VPT and SPJ conditions. The vast majority scored above 75% accuracy in all sessions. We excluded three participants from the final analysis because fewer than 75% of their trials were usable in all sessions due to a combination of incorrect or missing responses and a high number of IED-marked trials (Janca et al., 2015). The consistently high performance indicates participants understood the task. Additionally, all participants were intact on visuospatial perception subtests - Picture Completion and Block Design - from the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale (WAIS-III) (Wechsler, 1997). Even though some participants were below normative range on various IQ scales, our supplementary analysis (Supplementary Analysis and Results, section 2.1), shows that excluding these participants, the accuracy results remained the same. We therefore suggest that our findings may extend to neurotypical populations and propose that future VPT studies test left/right relation Congruence effects in both VPT and SPJ tasks with neurotypical participants.

A second limitation concerns the experimental design. As described in the Methods, the Overhead and Horizontal stimuli differed across both objective and subjective dimensions. The goal object varied in size between Overhead and Horizontal, and the scene was shown entirely in Overhead but only partially in Horizontal. Additionally, depending on the VPT target angle, the goal appeared closer to the arena mid-line in some trials, an effect more pronounced in Horizontal than in Overhead. These differences may have affected the left/right judgments from the Self-perspective (See Supplementary Analysis and Results, sections 2.2 and 2.3 for the effects of Overhead/Horizontal and Angle of view).

To continue with the implications of these results for future directions in VPT and other ToM research, as a continuation of this work, we plan to examine whether significant brain responses in the iEEG data of these participants—particularly from the TPJ (ROI PTPC in Gunia et al., 2024) and other brain areas involved in both VPT and SPJ—distinguish between Congruent and Incongruent left/right conditions in both tasks. Next, we propose conducting scalp EEG, fMRI, and other neuroimaging studies measuring Self- and Other-related FBR vs. TBR and left/right Congruent and Incongruent conditions in VPT and SPJ tasks in neurotypical participants, to investigate whether similar brain mechanisms underlie the differentiation between Congruent and Incongruent beliefs and visuospatial perspectives. Third, returning to our suggestion that reducing the asymmetry between Self- and Other-perspective judgments would benefit future VPT research, we propose assessing the additive effects of multisensory Congruence between Self- and Other-perspectives. Specifically, to test whether increasing Congruence across various aspects of multisensory representations—beyond the correct response domain—would improve Other-perspective judgments. Lastly, we consider it worthwhile to examine whether making BR tasks more congruent across various representations, such as multisensory ones, would facilitate both Self- and Other-related BR judgments.

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Data and code availability statement

The data and code that support the findings of this study are available in the Open Science Framework at https://osf.io/wuapg/?view_only=8044ddd9cb35438e84ebe9f663e16c40.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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Supplementary Materials

1. Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Fig. 1. Mean accuracy and response times for left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials during VPT and SPJ, excluding 0° (all Congruent) and 180° (all Incongruent) trials. **Section a** shows percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for left/right Congruent (Cong, blue) and Incongruent (Incong, pink) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). The black asterisk (*) denotes significant difference between Congruent and Incongruent trials. Similar to full analysis including 0° and 180° VPT target angles, participants were more correct in Congruent compared to Incongruent trials during both VPT and SPJ. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. The black asterisk denotes significant difference between the left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials and the red one - significant difference between VPT and SPJ. In VPT, participants showed the same trend as in the full analysis—faster responses in Congruent than Incongruent trials—though this difference was no longer significant. In SPJ, participants remained significantly faster on Congruent compared to Incongruent trials. As in the full analysis, responses were faster in SPJ than in VPT.

Supplementary Fig. 2. Mean accuracy and response times for left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials during VPT and SPJ, plotted separately for each VPT target angle. **Section a** shows percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for left/right Congruent (Cong, blue) and Incongruent (Incong, pink) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). Although the SPJ condition at the 135° VPT target angle showed a reversed trend—where Congruent trials featured the goal closer to the central line than Incongruent trials—accuracy across all angles was higher in Congruent than in Incongruent trials, for both VPT and SPJ. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. In counter-clockwise VPT trials, Congruent trials showed the trend to be faster than Incongruent ones, whereas in clockwise trials, this trend diminished. When results were pooled across all angles, participants were faster in Congruent compared to Incongruent trials in the VPT condition. In SPJ, at angles where the goal was positioned closer to the central line in the Congruent condition (135° and 225°), Congruent trials tended to be slower than Incongruent ones. When pooled across all angles, SPJ trials showed faster responses in Incongruent compared to Congruent conditions. Overall, participants responded faster in SPJ than in VPT.

2. Supplementary Analyses and Results

2.1 The effect of left/right congruence on Self and Other perspective judgments in the subset of participants whose scores fell within the normative range on various IQ scales

As the research question addressed in this paper was derived from the previous iEEG findings, the presented behavioral data come from patients with epilepsy. To evaluate how their cognitive functioning compares to that of the neurotypical population, we assessed their performance across various standardized scales. All participants included in the main analysis were within the normative range for their age group on visuospatial perception subtests from the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale – Third Edition (WAIS-III) (Wechsler, 1997), specifically the Picture Completion and Block Design subtests.

Eight participants showed the below normative range performance on at least one of the following: Full Scale IQ, Verbal IQ, or Performance IQ scores from WAIS-III, or the Rey–

Osterrieth Complex Figure Test (Osterrieth, 1944, Rey, 1941). To examine whether their below-normal performance on these scales influenced our results across participants, we excluded these eight participants and conducted a linear mixed model (LMM) analysis to assess the effect of left/right relation Congruence between Self- and Other-perspectives on both types of perspective judgment.

For the accuracy data, excluding trials with no responses, the best-fit random slope model included Congruence and Perspective as fixed effects, their interaction, and Participant as a random effect with a random slope for Congruence: Accuracy \sim Congruence * Perspective + (1 + Congruence | ParticipantID). This model showed similar results as the one reported in the main text, including all 26 participants. Namely, the model revealed a significant fixed effect of Congruence at the reference level SPJ, with participants being less accurate on Incongruent trials compared to Congruent trials ($b = -0.03758$, $SE = 0.01567$, $t(29.97) = -2.40$, $p = 0.023$) (Supplementary Fig. 4). The similar effect was observed when comparing Congruence averaged over both levels of Perspective ($b = 0.0386$, $SE = 0.0138$, $t(18.2) = 2.794$, $p = 0.0119$). Neither effect of Perspective was significant at the reference level Congruent trials nor interaction between Perspective and Congruence.

For response times (RTs) of only correct responses, the best-fit model was a random intercept model with Congruence, Perspective, and their interaction as fixed effects, and Participant as a random effect: RT \sim Congruence * Perspective + (1 | ParticipantID). This model had comparable results to the one reported in the main text, including all 26 participants. Namely, the model showed on the verge of significance fixed effect of Congruence at the reference level SPJ ($b = -0.02835$, $SE = 0.01537$, $t(3627.15) = -1.84$, $p = 0.0652$), and a significant fixed effect of Perspective at the reference level Congruent trials ($b = 0.28720$, $SE = 0.01531$, $t(3627.13) = 18.75$, $p < 0.001$). The Congruence \times Perspective interaction was also significant ($b = 0.10569$, $SE = 0.02187$, $t(3627.13) = 4.83$, $p < 0.001$). The post hoc analysis showed that in the VPT condition RTs were slower for Incongruent trials ($b = -0.0773$, $SE = 0.0156$, $t(3627) = -4.973$, $p < 0.0001$). In the SPJ condition, the effect was reversed, although slightly below significance threshold (Supplementary Fig. 5). When averaged across both levels of Congruence, participants were overall faster in the VPT condition compared to the SPJ condition ($b = -0.340$, $SE = 0.0109$, $t(3627) = -31.097$, $p < 0.000$).

Overall, the behavioral results from the 18 participants who performed within the normal range on all listed cognitive scales were consistent with those from the full sample, including the eight participants who showed below normal performance on the scales.

Supplementary Fig. 3. Mean accuracy and response times for left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials during VPT and SPJ, excluding eight participants who showed below-norm performance on at least one IQ test.

Section a shows Percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for left/right Congruent (Cong, blue) and Incongruent (Incong, pink) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). The black asterisk (*) denotes significant difference between Congruent and Incongruent trials. In this subsample of 18 participants who all performed within the normal range on all IQ tests, the same pattern emerged as in the full sample: participants were more accurate in Congruent than in Incongruent trials in both VPT and SPJ conditions. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. The black asterisk denotes significant difference between the left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials and the red one - significant difference between VPT and SPJ. Similar to the all participant analysis, in VPT, participants were faster in Congruent than in Incongruent trials. As in the full-sample analysis, participants were faster in Congruent compared to Incongruent trials during VPT. In SPJ, the same trend, Congruent being slower than Incongruent, was observed as in the full-sample analysis, but it no longer reached significance. Participants were faster in SPJ compared to VPT.

2.2 The effect of the Overhead and Horizontal view condition of the VPT experiment on RTs and Accuracy data

The VPT experiment, originally along with the SPJ and VPT perspective, had Overhead and Horizontal conditions, so that each stimulus was presented either in Overhead or Horizontal view. For the supplementary analysis, we conducted LMM analysis to measure the effect of View (Overhead/Horizontal) of the stimulus presentation on participants' Accuracy and RT measures. LMM best fit random slope model for Accuracy included Perspective and View as main effects, allowing interaction between them; Participant as a random effect, allowing random slope for View to vary for the participants - Accuracy ~ Perspective * View + (1 + View | ParticipantID). The model showed a significant fixed effect of Perspective at the reference level Overhead condition ($b = -0.02100$, $SE = 0.01046$, $t(5732.27) = -2.009$, $p = 0.0446$), the significant fixed effect of the View at the reference level SPJ ($b = -0.03929$, $SE = 0.01342$, $t(52.84) = -2.928$, $p = 0.0050$), and no significant interaction between the factors (Supplementary Fig. 4a, 5a). However, the comparison of the marginal means of Perspective averaged over both levels of the View did not show significant difference. The comparison of Horizontal and Overhead conditions averaged across both levels of Perspective was significant

but Post hoc analysis revealed that only in SPJ, the Overhead view was significantly more correct than Horizontal.

Next we built a similar random slope model for RTs on only correct responses - $RT \sim \text{Perspective} * \text{View} + (1 + \text{View} | \text{ParticipantID})$. The model showed the significant fixed effect of Perspective ($b = 0.2428$, $SE = 0.01313$, $t(5198) = 18.485$, $p < 0.001$) at the reference level Overhead condition. The fixed effect of the View was on the verge of significance at the reference level SPJ ($b = 0.03890$, $SE = 0.01938$, $t(43.25) = 2.007$, $p = 0.0511$). Overhead being on the verge of significance faster than Horizontal. Additionally, there was a significant interaction between the factors ($b = 0.08795$, $SE = 0.01869$, $t(5195) = 4.706$, $p < 0.001$). Post hoc analysis showed that when examining only the correct responses, participants were significantly faster in Overhead view compared to Horizontal only during VPT ($b = -0.1268$, $SE = 0.0195$, $t(44.2) = -6.511$, $p < .0001$) (Supplementary Fig. 4b, 5b). When averaged across both levels of the View plane, participants were significantly faster in SPJ than in VPT ($b = -0.287$, $SE = 0.00934$, $t(5203) = -30.707$, $p < 0.0001$).

Supplementary Fig. 4. Mean accuracy and response times for Overhead and Horizontal view trials during VPT and SPJ. Section a shows Percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for Overhead (Orange) and Horizontal (Cyan) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). The black asterisk (*) denotes significant difference between Overhead and Horizontal trials in SPJ condition. Participants were more correct in Overhead compared to Horizontal trials during SPJ. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. The black asterisk denotes significant

difference between Overhead and Horizontal trials in VPT condition and the red one - significant difference between VPT and SPJ. In VPT, participants were faster in Overhead than in Horizontal trials. Participants were faster in SPJ compared to VPT.

Supplementary Fig. 5. Mean accuracy and response times for Overhead and Horizontal view trials during VPT and SPJ, plotted separately for each VPT target angle. **Section a** shows Percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for Overhead (Orange) and Horizontal (Cyan) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). Although the goal appeared closer to the central line at almost all VPT target angles in the Horizontal view than in the Overhead view, this difference was more pronounced at 90°, 135°, 225°, and 270°, potentially complicating left/right judgments from the Self-perspective in the Horizontal view compared to the Overhead view. Participants were more correct in SPJ compared to VPT only in the Overhead view. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. Participants were faster in the Overhead than in the Horizontal view in the VPT condition. This difference may be due to visual features of the stimuli; for example, at 0° in the Horizontal view, the VPT target mark was not visible, requiring participants to imagine it behind them. This, along with the goal's proximity to the central line, may have complicated VPT judgments in the Horizontal vs. Overhead view. Participants responded faster in SPJ than in VPT.

2.2.1 Discussion for the effect of Overhead and Horizontal view condition of the VPT experiment

As discussed in Methods section 2.2, all stimuli in the VPT experiment were presented either in Overhead or Horizontal view (Fig. 1 in the main text). In this supplementary analysis, we compared the effects of Overhead and Horizontal view conditions during SPJ and VPT. The LMM analysis showed that in SPJ conditions, participants were more accurate in the Overhead view compared to the Horizontal view (Supplementary Fig. 4a, 5a). Additionally, they were faster in the Overhead view compared to the Horizontal view in the VPT condition (Supplementary Fig. 4b, 5b).

In the Introduction Section 1.2, drawing on May's (2004) suggestion that object direction disparity—i.e., the incongruence in direction of an object between Self- and Other-perspective—constitutes one source of egocentric interference during VPT, we suggested that Congruence in the plane of view —i.e., Overhead vs. Horizontal view planes—may represent a potential source of the Congruence effect in multisensory representations between Self- and Other-perspectives in certain VPT tasks. This is because, in tasks like ours where participants

are explicitly instructed to make VPT judgments, both in Horizontal and Overhead view conditions, by imagining themselves standing within a virtual scene, if participants follow the instructions, likely, in the Overhead view condition, they mentally represent both the scene and themselves in it, in a horizontal format. This may introduce incongruence between different types of representations: the participant's actual visual input - a horizontal representation of the real world, another actual visual input- an overhead representation of the perceived stimuli, and the imagined horizontal representation of the virtual scene. Based on this, we would have expected Overhead trials to be more difficult compared to Horizontal. Contrary to this, our results showed the opposite.

However, we are cautious in interpreting these results because the Overhead and Horizontal view stimuli differed from each other on various objective as well as subjective measures, as described in the Methods section 2.2. Namely, the goal was of a different size in Overhead vs Horizontal view, the scene was shown completely in Overhead view, whereas it was only partially shown in Horizontal. The goal appeared closer to the central line at almost all VPT target angles in the Horizontal view than in the Overhead view, with this difference being more pronounced at certain angles (e.g., 90°, 135°, 225°, 270°). As shown in Supplementary Fig. 5a, SPJ judgments had the trend be more difficult in those VPT target angle trials where, in the Horizontal view, the goal appeared closer to the central line than in the Overhead view, potentially complicating left/right judgments from the Self-perspective. Additionally, at 0° in the Horizontal view compared to the Overhead view, the VPT target mark was not visible, and participants had to imagine it behind them, potentially complicating VPT judgments at this angle Fig. 5. Therefore, due to these potential confounding variables, we cannot conclude that the observed difference reflects the effect of Congruence in the view plane; it is more likely specific to the Overhead versus Horizontal stimuli used in our experiment.

2.3 The effect of the VPT target angle on RTs and Accuracy data

The VPT experiment presented here, similar to many other VPT tasks (Kessler and Thomson, 2010, Michelon and Zacks, 2006, Seymour et al., 2018), was constructed such that stimuli were presented at varying VPT target angles (i.e., landmark presentation angles; for details, see the Methods section 2.2). The Congruence in the angle of view between Self- and Other-perspective, also referred to as the Angular disparity effect, is widely studied in the VPT literature. VPT studies consistently report that with increasing VPT target angle, participants require more time to make Other-perspective judgments (Michelon and Zacks, 2006, Kessler and Rutherford, 2010, Seymour et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016).

To estimate how increasing VPT target angle influenced participants' Accuracy and RTs, we followed the example of previous studies (Kessler and Thomson, 2010, Seymour et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016) and grouped the clockwise and counterclockwise 45-degree trials (i.e., 315° and 45°) as Low Degree, the 90-degree trials (270° and 90°) as Middle Degree, and the 135-

degree trials (225° and 135°) as High Degree. We then constructed separate LMMs for Accuracy and RT, including Degree (Low, Middle, High) and Perspective (SPJ, VPT) as fixed effects.

The best-fit random intercept LMM for Accuracy, with Perspective and Degree as fixed effects, allowing interaction between them and Participant as a random effect - Accuracy ~ Perspective * Degree + (1 | ParticipantID), revealed a fixed effect of Perspective ($b = -0.04241$, $SE = 0.01418$, $t(4313) = -2.991$, $p = 0.0028$), indicating lower accuracy in the VPT condition relative to SPJ at the reference level High Degree. There was also a significant effect of Low Degree compared to the High Degree reference at the reference level SPJ ($b = -0.04459$, $SE = 0.01423$, $t(4313) = -3.133$, $p = 0.0017$), while the effect of Middle Degree was not significant. There were significant interactions between Perspective and Low Degree ($b = 0.1176$, $SE = 0.02016$, $t(4313) = 5.831$, $p < 0.001$), and Perspective and Middle Degree ($b = 0.06042$, $SE = 0.02014$, $t(4313) = 3.001$, $p = 0.0027$), indicating that the relationship between Perspective and Accuracy varied across degree levels (Supplementary Fig. 6a, 7a). The post hoc analysis for the effect of Perspective showed that, although at the High Degree, participants were more accurate in SPJ than in VPT, the opposite was true at the Low Degree ($b = -0.0752$, $SE = 0.0143$, $t(4313) = -5.243$, $p < 0.0001$). No significant difference was found at the Middle Degree. The post hoc analysis for the effect of Degree revealed that, in the VPT condition, participants were more accurate in Low ($b = -0.07298$, $SE = 0.0143$, $t(4313) = -5.109$, $p < 0.0001$) and Middle Degree trials compared to High Degree trials ($b = -0.06485$, $SE = 0.0143$, $t(4313) = -4.524$, $p < 0.0001$). There was no significant difference at the Middle Degree. In contrast, in the SPJ condition, participants were more accurate in Middle Degree trials compared to Low Degree trials ($b = -0.04902$, $SE = 0.0142$, $t(4313) = -3.447$, $p = 0.0017$) and in High Degree compared to Low Degree trials, as reflected by the mixed-effects model estimates reported above.

The best-fit random slope model for RTs of the correct responses had Perspective and Degree as fixed effects, allowing interaction between them. The model additionally had Participant as a random effect and a random slope for Degree for participants - RT ~ Perspective * Degree + (1 + Degree | ParticipantID). The model showed the fixed effect of Perspective at the reference level High Degree ($b = 0.36276$, $SE = 0.01791$, $t(3935.20) = 20.250$, $p < 0.001$). Participants were faster in SPJ compared to VPT. The Middle Degree was also significantly different compared to the reference level High Degree ($b = -0.06547$, $SE = 0.01811$, $t(444.88) = -3.616$, $p < 0.001$). The effect of the Low Degree compared to the reference High Degree was not significant. Additionally, there was significant interaction between Perspective and Low Degree ($b = -0.18317$, $SE = 0.02537$, $t(3935.26) = -7.219$, $p < 0.001$), showing that participants exhibited different relation between VPT and SPJ on Low Degree than on High Degree. And, there was significant interaction between Perspective and Middle Degree ($b = -0.07038$, $SE = 0.02519$, $t(3935.18) = -2.794$, $p = 0.0052$), showing that participants exhibited different relation between VPT and SPJ on Middle Degree than on High Degree (Supplementary Fig. 6b, 7b). The post hoc analysis showed that during VPT, participants were significantly faster

in Low ($b = 0.1567$, $SE = 0.0197$, $t(146) = 7.945$, $p < 0.0001$) and Middle Degree trials ($b = 0.1358$, $SE = 0.0185$, $t(479) = 7.355$, $p < 0.0001$) compared to High Degree trials, and no difference between the Low and Middle Degree trials. Contrary, during SPJ, they were significantly faster in Middle Degree trials compared to High ($b = 0.0655$, $SE = 0.0181$, $t(445) = 3.616$, $p = 0.0010$) and Low Degree trials ($b = 0.0919$, $SE = 0.0184$, $t(484) = 4.991$, $p < 0.0001$), and no difference between the High and Low Degree trials.

Supplementary Fig. 6. Mean accuracy and response times for High Degree, Middle Degree and Low Degree trials during VPT and SPJ. Section a shows

Percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for High Degree (HighDeg, grey), Middle Degree (MiddleDeg, magenta) and Low Degree (LowDeg, green) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ). In VPT, the black asterisk (*) indicates significant differences between High Degree and both Low Degree and Middle Degree trials; participants were more accurate in Low and Middle Degree trials than in High Degree trials. In SPJ, the black asterisk indicates significant differences between Low Degree and both High Degree and Middle Degree trials; participants were more accurate in High and Middle Degree trials than in Low Degree trials. The green asterisk indicates a significant difference between VPT and SPJ at Low Degree, and the grey asterisk indicates a significant difference between perspectives at High Degree. Participants were more accurate in VPT than SPJ at Low Degree, whereas the reverse was true at High Degree. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. In VPT, the black asterisk indicates significant differences between High Degree and both Low and Middle Degree trials; participants were slower in High Degree trials than in the other two Degree levels. In SPJ, the black asterisk indicates significant differences between Middle Degree and both High and Low Degree trials; participants were slower in High and Low Degree trials than in Middle Degree trials. The red asterisk indicates an overall significant difference between VPT and SPJ, with participants responding faster in SPJ than in VPT.

Fig. 7. Mean accuracy and response times for High Degree, Middle Degree and Low Degree trials during VPT and SPJ, plotted separately for left/right

Congruent and Incongruent trials. **Section a** shows Percent mean accuracy (%) with standard error of the mean (SEM) for High Degree (HighDeg, grey), Middle Degree (MiddleDeg, magenta) and Low Degree (LowDeg, green) trials during visuospatial perspective-taking (VPT) and Self-perspective judgments (SPJ) plotted for left/right Congruent (Cong) and Incongruent (Incong) trials separately. Accuracy differences across Degree levels in SPJ likely reflect visual properties of the stimuli and their left/right Congruence. In half of both Low- and High-Degree trials, the goal appeared near the central line from the Self-perspective. However, in the Low-Degree condition, these cases were also left/right Incongruent with the Other-perspective, apparently making them more difficult. This combination of ambiguous Self-perspective left/right relation and Incongruence likely explains why participants were more accurate in VPT than in SPJ for Low-Degree trials. In contrast, for High-Degree trials, participants were more accurate in SPJ than VPT, presumably because here the Self-perspective ambiguity occurred in left/right Congruent trials rather than in Incongruent trials, which was the case in the Low-Degree case. **Section b** shows the mean response times (RT) values with SEM in seconds. Considering only correct responses, participants were faster in SPJ than in VPT for all Degrees supporting the interpretation that reduced SPJ accuracy in Low Degree may stem from the combination of ambiguous Self-perspective left/right relation and left/right Incongruence with the Other-perspective—affecting accuracy but not speed when participants responded correctly.

2.3.1 Discussion for the effect of the VPT target angle on VPT and SPJ

In this supplementary analysis, we examined the effect of VPT target angle during both VPT and SPJ conditions. Accuracy and RT results showed that in the VPT condition, Low and Middle Degree trials were easier than High Degree trials (Supplementary Fig. 6, 7). This replicates the well-documented Angular disparity, i.e., Congruence in angle of view effect, whereby taking the Other-perspective becomes more difficult at higher VPT target angles (Michelon and Zacks, 2006, Kessler and Thomson, 2010, Kessler and Rutherford, 2010, Seymour et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016).

Importantly, in our experiment—unlike some of the previous VPT studies—higher VPT target angle trials were not exclusively left/right Incongruent, nor were lower angle trials

exclusively left/right Congruent, as discussed in Discussion section 4.1. In this experiment, both left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials were across nearly all VPT target angles, with the exception of 0° and 180°. Excluding these two angles allowed us to combine left/right Congruent and Incongruent trials across each level of the Degree variable. Even without selective addition of the left/right Incongruence to higher angles, we still observed the Angular disparity effect in the VPT condition. However, we remain cautious in attributing this result solely to Angular disparity, because as Fig. 1 shows, in our experiment, distance Incongruence adds up to the angle of view Incongruence (See, Fig. 1, and Discussion, section 4.1).

In contrast, in the SPJ condition, the participants were less accurate in Low Degree trials compared to High Degree trials (Supplementary Fig. 6a, 7a). This difference is not well visible on the RTs (Supplementary Fig. 6b, 7b). The observed Accuracy differences across Degree levels in SPJ are likely largely influenced by visual features of the stimuli and their left/right Congruence. Specifically, in High Degree trials, the goal that is left/right Congruent with the Other-perspective appears close to the central axis of the arena, potentially making left/right judgments from the Self-perspective ambiguous (Supplementary Fig. 7). On the other hand, in Low Degree trials, the goal is left/right Incongruent with the Other-perspective and also appears close to the central line, introducing ambiguity in Self-perspective judgments (Supplementary Fig. 7). Thus, although the goal appears near the central line from the Self-perspective in half of both Low and High Degree trials, in the Low Degree condition it is additionally Incongruent with the Other-perspective—apparently making those trials more difficult.

This ambiguity in left/right relation from Self-perspective in addition to the left/right relation Incongruence likely explains why participants were more accurate in the VPT condition than in the SPJ condition for Low Degree trials (Supplementary Fig. 6a, 7a). On High Degree trials, the reverse pattern was observed, presumably because adopting the Other-perspective in the presence of large angular and distance Incongruences, which potentially implies increased need to mentally transform the body in a VPT target location and orientation, is cognitively demanding (Kessler and Thomson, 2010, Kessler and Rutherford, 2010). In this case, determining the goal's left/right position from the Self-perspective may be relatively easier because SPJ is not supposed to require body transformation and on High Degrees the ambiguity in left/right relation from Self-perspective adds up to left/right Congruent trials, not to the Incongruent trials - as it is on Low Degrees. Fig. 6b, 7b for RT show that when only the correct responses were taken, participants were faster in SPJ compared to VPT on all degrees. This again supports the explanation that on the Low VPT target degrees, the low Accuracy results for SPJ may be due to ambiguous left/right relation of a goal to Self-perspective combining with left/right Incongruence with Other-perspective, which influenced Accuracy but if participants were correct, they were faster.

Supplementary References

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